

Novel insights into mucin O-glycans recognition by commensal bacteria from the human gut microbiome

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The human gut microbiome plays a vital role in targeting and utilizing glycans from our diet and mucin glycans from the mucosal intestinal layer, impacting host nutrition, immunity, and infection susceptibility^{1,2}. The exploitation of mucin O-glycans by intestinal bacteria and their influence on host crosstalk remain largely unexplored at the molecular level.

Abundant colonic bacteria, like *Bacteroides* species, possess polysaccharide utilization loci (PULs) that enable adaptation to glycan substrate variations^{1,2}. Each PUL encodes proteins for recognizing and breaking down specific glycans, including carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) with carbohydrate-binding modules (CBMs) and other glycan-binding proteins^{1,2}.

We report the functional and structural characterization of newly identified glycan-binding proteins from *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* with increased activity on mucin O-glycans under a low-fiber diet. Using an integrative strategy, we combined bioinformatic analysis, high-throughput protein production, ligand discovery via glycan microarrays³⁻⁵, and structural characterization by X-ray crystallography⁶. Our findings elucidate the molecular basis for the unique specificities of glycan-binding proteins targeting fucosylated Lewis A and mucin O-GalNAc-Thr/Ser core structures.

Uncovering the molecular determinants for mucin O-glycan recognition by bacterial systems can help understand the role of commensals in gut health and potentiate new therapeutic and diagnostic strategies.

References

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